

Finite Difference Method for Neutrosophic Fuzzy Second Order Differential Equation under Generalized Hukuhara Differentiability

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Abstract

This paper solves the boundary value problem of the second-order differential equation under the neutrosophic fuzzy boundary condition. The proposed solution is approximated using the finite difference method but deneutrosophication utilizing strongly generalized Hukuhara differentiability. The error calculation is then processed by comparing the proposed numerical solution with the analytical solution presented in our earlier work [20].

Keywords: Fuzzy Differential Equations (FDEs); Neutrosophic Boundary Conditions; Hukuhara Differentiability; Finite Difference Method (FDM).

1. Introduction

Modeling real problems as ideal mathematical cases cannot help in applying or finding real solutions, and this was the reason for initiating the concept of fuzzy sets and derivatives with Zadeh [1]. Several later works aimed to widen the concept of differentiability, especially Hukuhara [2-6] who developed the concept of the difference between fuzzy sets, then he initiated Hukuhara differentiability. Following that, both Stefanoni and Bede in [4,5,6] developed the generalized Hukuhara differentiability.

On the other hand, several researchers applied many numerical methods to solve fuzzy problems. The numerical solutions of the fuzzy initial value problem (FIVP) by Euler's method were studied by Ma [17]. Abbasbandy and Allahviranloo [14, 15] used the Taylor

and fourth-order Runge-Kutta methods to solve FIVPs. The author of [19] applied the Runge-Kutta method for more general problems and proved the convergence for the n-stage Runge-Kutta method. In [16], numerical solutions of fuzzy differential equations (FDEs) were presented by employing the predictor-corrector method. The dependency problem in fuzzy computation was discussed by Ahmadi and Hasan [17], where Euler's method based on Zadeh's extension principle was used for finding the numerical solution of FIVPs. Omar and Hasan [18] adopted the same computation method to derive the fourth-order Runge-Kutta method for FIVP.

Uncertainty, vagueness, and incompleteness in data increase the requirement for more generalized fuzzy ideas. That motivated Smarandache [10,11,12,13] to initiate a neutrosophic concept, which depends not only on membership, but also on three different memberships Truth, False, and Indeterminacy which facilitates modelling more complicated uncertain data, and this concept is called the neutrosophic fuzzy set.

In this paper, a numerical solution for a neutrosophic fuzzy second-order differential equation is proposed under strongly generalized differentiability by using the finite difference method. The results are compared with the analytical solutions of the same numerical examples presented in our previous results [20].

2. Preliminaries

Some relevant basic concepts are presented in this section to preface the mathematical tools of neutrosophic theory which are essential for the issues of this essay.

2.1 Definition [12].

Let X be a universe set and a neutrosophic set A on X is defined as $A = \{(T_A(x), I_A(x), F_A(x)): x \in X\}$ represents the degree of membership $T_A(x)$, the degree of indeterministic $I_A(x)$ and the degree of non-membership $F_A(x)$. Such that $0 \leq T_A(x) + I_A(x) + F_A(x) \leq 3$.

2.2 Definition [11]

The (α, β, γ) -cuts are fixed values on the set A where $A_{\alpha, \beta, \gamma} = \{(T_A(x), I_A(x), F_A(x)): x \in X, T_A(x) \geq \alpha, I_A(x) \leq \beta, F_A(x) \leq \gamma\}$ which define each of $T_A(x), I_A(x), F_A(x)$ in terms of lower and upper functions of (α, β, γ) -cuts.

2.3 Definition [13]

A neutrosophic set A defined on a universal set of real numbers \mathbf{R} is said to be a neutrosophic number and:

- i) A is normal if $x_a \in R, T_A(x_a) = 1, I_A(x_a) = F_A(x_a) = 0$.
- ii) A is a convex set on truth function $T_A(x)$ where $T_A(\lambda x_1 + (1 - \lambda)x_2) \geq \min(T_A(x_1), T_A(x_2)); \forall x_1, x_2 \in R, \lambda \in [0,1]$
- iii) A is a concave set on indeterministic and falsity functions $I_A(x), F_A(x)$, satisfying $I_A(\lambda x_1 + (1 - \lambda)x_2) \geq \max(I_A(x_1), I_A(x_2)), F_A(\lambda x_1 + (1 - \lambda)x_2) \geq \max(F_A(x_1), F_A(x_2))$, this is also $\forall x_1, x_2 \in R, \lambda \in [0,1]$.

2.4 Definition [7]

Let A be a Generalized triangular neutrosophic number $A_{GTN} = (a, b, c: \omega, \eta, \xi)$

$$T_A(x) = \begin{cases} \frac{x-a}{b-a} \omega & a \leq x < b \\ \omega & x = b \\ \frac{c-x}{c-b} \omega & b < x \leq c \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

$$I_A(x) = \begin{cases} \frac{b-x}{b-a} \eta & a \leq x < b \\ \eta & x = b \\ \frac{b-x}{b-c} \eta & b < x \leq c \\ 1 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

$$F_A(x) = \begin{cases} \frac{b-x}{b-a} \xi & a \leq x < b \\ \xi & x = b \\ \frac{b-x}{b-c} \xi & b < x \leq c \\ 1 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

The (α, β, γ) -cuts on the generalized triangular neutrosophic number can be written as

$$A_{\alpha, \beta, \gamma} = [A(\alpha), \overline{A(\alpha)}], [A(\beta), \overline{A(\beta)}], [A(\gamma), \overline{A(\gamma)}],$$

$$[A(\alpha), \overline{A(\alpha)}] = \left[\left(a + \frac{\alpha}{\omega} (b - a) \right), \left(c - \frac{\alpha}{\omega} (c - b) \right) \right],$$

$$[A(\beta), \overline{A(\beta)}] = \left[\left(a + \frac{1-\beta}{1-\eta} (b - a) \right), \left(c - \frac{1-\beta}{1-\eta} (c - b) \right) \right],$$

$$[A(\gamma), \overline{A(\gamma)}] = \left[\left(a + \frac{1-\gamma}{1-\xi} (b - a) \right), \left(c - \frac{1-\gamma}{1-\xi} (c - b) \right) \right].$$

2.5 Definition 5 [8]

Let A be a generalized trapezoidal neutrosophic number $A_{GTRN} = (a, b, c, d: \omega, \eta, \xi)$ with

$$T_A(x) = \begin{cases} \frac{x-a}{b-a} \omega & a \leq x \leq b \\ \omega & b \leq x \leq c \\ \frac{d-x}{d-c} \omega & c \leq x \leq d \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

$$I_A(x) = \begin{cases} \frac{b-x}{b-a} \eta & a \leq x \leq b \\ \eta & b \leq x \leq c \\ \frac{c-x}{c-d} \eta & c \leq x \leq d \\ 1 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

$$F_A(x) = \begin{cases} \frac{b-x}{b-a} \xi & a \leq x \leq b \\ \xi & b \leq x \leq c \\ \frac{c-x}{c-d} \xi & c \leq x \leq d \\ 1 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

The (α, β, γ) -cuts on the generalized trapezoidal neutrosophic number can be represented as

$$A_{\alpha, \beta, \gamma} = [\underline{A}(\alpha), \overline{A}(\alpha)], [\underline{A}(\beta), \overline{A}(\beta)], [\underline{A}(\gamma), \overline{A}(\gamma)],$$

$$[\underline{A}(\alpha), \overline{A}(\alpha)] = \left[\left(a + \frac{\alpha}{\omega} (b - a) \right), \left(d - \frac{\alpha}{\omega} (d - c) \right) \right],$$

$$[\underline{A}(\beta), \overline{A}(\beta)] = \left[\left(a + \frac{1-\beta}{1-\eta} (b - a) \right), \left(d - \frac{1-\beta}{1-\eta} (d - c) \right) \right],$$

$$[\underline{A}(\gamma), \overline{A}(\gamma)] = \left[\left(a + \frac{1-\gamma}{1-\xi} (b - a) \right), \left(d - \frac{1-\gamma}{1-\xi} (d - c) \right) \right].$$

2.6 Definition [6]

Let $F: (a, b) \rightarrow \mathcal{F}(R)$, if the next limits

$$\lim_{h \rightarrow 0^+} \frac{F(x_0 + h) \ominus_H F(x_0)}{h}, \quad \lim_{h \rightarrow 0^+} \frac{F(x_0) \ominus_H F(x_0 - h)}{h}$$

exist and equal some elements $F'_H(x_0) \in \mathcal{F}(R)$, then F is Hukuhara differentiable at $x_0 \in (a, b)$, and $F'_H(x_0)$ is its derivative at $x_0 \in (a, b)$.

2.7 Theorem [5]

Let $F: (a, b) \rightarrow \mathcal{F}(R)$ be a generalized Hukuhara differentiable function if and only if one of the following conditions is satisfied

- i. $\underline{f}'_\alpha(x)$ is increasing and $\overline{f}'_\alpha(x)$ is decreasing
- ii. $\underline{f}'_\alpha(x)$ is decreasing and $\overline{f}'_\alpha(x)$ is increasing

Implies to,

$$[F'_{gH}(x)]_\alpha = \left[\min \left(\underline{f}'_\alpha(x), \overline{f}'_\alpha(x) \right), \max \left(\underline{f}'_\alpha(x), \overline{f}'_\alpha(x) \right) \right].$$

This concept is closer to the generalized differentiability, but it probably focuses on the cases of the function and both of these differentiabilitys change the concept of derivatives, so let us show these changes in the next definition of generalized Hukuhara derivatives.

2.8 Definition [6]

The generalized Hukuhara first derivative of a fuzzy parametric function is defined as:

$$f'(x_0) = \lim_{h \rightarrow 0} \frac{f(x_0+h) \ominus_{gh} f(x_0)}{h},$$

From this definition, two classes can be defined:

(i)-differentiable at x_0 : $[f'(x_0)]_\alpha = [\underline{f}'_\alpha(x_0), \overline{f}'_\alpha(x_0)]$

(ii)-differentiable at x_0 : $[f'(x_0)]_\alpha = [\overline{f}'_\alpha(x_0), \underline{f}'_\alpha(x_0)]$

2.9 Definition [6]

The generalized Hukuhara second derivative of the fuzzy function is defined as:

$$f''(x_0) = \lim_{h \rightarrow 0} \frac{f'(x_0+h) \ominus_{gh} f'(x_0)}{h},$$

According to the last two definitions, the following classes can be selected:

$f'(x_0)$ is (i)-differentiable if:

$$f''(x_0) = \left\{ \begin{array}{l} [\underline{f}''_\alpha(x_0), \overline{f}''_\alpha(x_0)] \text{ if } f \text{ is (i) - differentiable of class (1,1)} \\ [\overline{f}''_\alpha(x_0), \underline{f}''_\alpha(x_0)] \text{ if } f \text{ is (ii) - differentiable of class (2,2)} \end{array} \right\}.$$

$f'(x_0)$ is (ii)-differentiable if:

$$f''(x_0) = \left\{ \begin{array}{l} [\overline{f}''_\alpha(x_0), \underline{f}''_\alpha(x_0)] \text{ if } f \text{ is (i) - differentiable of class (1,2)} \\ [\underline{f}''_\alpha(x_0), \overline{f}''_\alpha(x_0)] \text{ if } f \text{ is (ii) - differentiable of class (2,1)} \end{array} \right\}.$$

2.10 Definition [7]

The solution $\tilde{y}(t, \alpha, \beta, \gamma)$ of the neutrosophic fuzzy differential equation is strong only if,

$$\frac{\partial y}{\partial \alpha} > 0, \frac{d\tilde{y}}{d\alpha} < 0 \text{ but } \frac{\partial y}{\partial \beta} < 0, \frac{d\tilde{y}}{d\beta} > 0 \text{ and } \frac{\partial y}{\partial \gamma} < 0, \frac{d\tilde{y}}{d\gamma} > 0.$$

3. Finite Difference Method Under Generalized Hukuhara Differentiability

The generalized Hukuhara differentiability is first utilized on the neutrosophic differential problem, which in turn will transform it into classes of differential equations. Then, the solution can be obtained by applying the finite difference method to these classes of the differential equation.

As an example and for a second-order differential equation that has neutrosophic input adopting the generalized Hukuhara differentiability, this problem is split into four classes, each class contains two certain equations. Then, the normal finite difference method (FDM) $y'' = \frac{y_{i+1}-2y_i+y_{i-1}}{h^2}$, $y' = \frac{y_{i+1}-y_{i-1}}{2h}$

is considered on each certain first and second derivatives of the function.

Under generalized Hukuhara differentiability

$$\tilde{y}''(t, \alpha, \beta, \gamma) = p\tilde{y}'(t, \alpha, \beta, \gamma) + q\tilde{y}(t, \alpha, \beta, \gamma),$$

$$\tilde{y}(t_0) = \tilde{a} ; \tilde{y}(T) = \tilde{b}.$$

Where the parameters are positive constants.

A. Class (1,1)

$$\overline{\tilde{y}''}(t, \alpha, \beta, \gamma) = p.\overline{\tilde{y}'}(t, \alpha, \beta, \gamma) + q.\overline{\tilde{y}}(t, \alpha, \beta, \gamma),$$

$$\overline{\tilde{y}}(t_0, \alpha, \beta, \gamma) = \overline{\tilde{a}} \quad \overline{\tilde{y}}(T, \alpha, \beta, \gamma) = \overline{\tilde{b}},$$

$$\underline{\tilde{y}''}(t, \alpha, \beta, \gamma) = p.\underline{\tilde{y}'}(t, \alpha, \beta, \gamma) + q.\underline{\tilde{y}}(t, \alpha, \beta, \gamma),$$

$$\underline{\tilde{y}}(t_0, \alpha, \beta, \gamma) = \underline{\tilde{a}} \quad \underline{\tilde{y}}(T, \alpha, \beta, \gamma) = \underline{\tilde{b}}.$$

By using the traditional finite difference method we have the following results

$$\overline{\tilde{y}}(t, \alpha, \beta, \gamma) = v \text{ and } \underline{\tilde{y}}(t, \alpha, \beta, \gamma) = u$$

$$\underline{\tilde{y}''}(t, \alpha, \beta, \gamma) = p.\underline{\tilde{y}'}(t, \alpha, \beta, \gamma) + q.\underline{\tilde{y}}(t, \alpha, \beta, \gamma) \tag{1}$$

$$\frac{u_{i+1}-2u_i+u_{i-1}}{h^2} = p \frac{u_{i+1}-u_{i-1}}{2h} + qu_i \tag{2}$$

$$u_{i+1} - 2u_i + u_{i-1} = \frac{ph}{2}u_{i+1} - \frac{ph}{2}u_{i-1} + qh^2u_i \tag{3}$$

$$\left(1 - \frac{ph}{2}\right)u_{i+1} - (2 + qh^2)u_i + \left(1 + \frac{ph}{2}\right)u_{i-1} = 0 \tag{4}$$

Where $h = \Delta x$ and $i = 1, 2, 3$

$$\begin{bmatrix} -(2 + qh^2) & \left(1 - \frac{ph}{2}\right) & 0 \\ \left(1 + \frac{ph}{2}\right) & -(2 + qh^2) & \left(1 - \frac{ph}{2}\right) \\ 0 & \left(1 + \frac{ph}{2}\right) & -(2 + qh^2) \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} u_1 \\ u_2 \\ u_3 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} -\left(1 + \frac{ph}{2}\right)u_0 \\ 0 \\ -\left(1 - \frac{ph}{2}\right)u_4 \end{bmatrix}$$

Where, $u_0 = \underline{\tilde{a}}$ and $u_4 = \underline{\tilde{b}}$

$$\overline{\tilde{y}''}(t, \alpha, \beta, \gamma) = p.\overline{\tilde{y}'}(t, \alpha, \beta, \gamma) + q.\overline{\tilde{y}}(t, \alpha, \beta, \gamma) \tag{5}$$

$$\frac{v_{i+1}-2v_i+v_{i-1}}{h^2} = p \frac{v_{i+1}-v_{i-1}}{2h} + qv_i \tag{6}$$

$$v_{i+1} - 2v_i + v_{i-1} = \frac{ph}{2} v_{i+1} - \frac{ph}{2} v_{i-1} + qh^2 v_i \tag{7}$$

$$\left(1 - \frac{ph}{2}\right) v_{i+1} - (2 + qh^2)v_i + \left(1 + \frac{ph}{2}\right) v_{i-1} = 0 \tag{8}$$

$$\begin{bmatrix} -(2 + qh^2) & \left(1 - \frac{ph}{2}\right) & 0 \\ \left(1 + \frac{ph}{2}\right) & -(2 + qh^2) & \left(1 - \frac{ph}{2}\right) \\ 0 & \left(1 + \frac{ph}{2}\right) & -(2 + qh^2) \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} v_1 \\ v_2 \\ v_3 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} -\left(1 + \frac{ph}{2}\right) v_0 \\ 0 \\ -\left(1 - \frac{ph}{2}\right) v_4 \end{bmatrix}$$

Where, $v_0 = \bar{a}$ and $v_4 = \bar{b}$

B. Class (1,2)

$$\underline{\bar{y}}''(t, \alpha, \beta, \gamma) = p. \underline{\bar{y}}'(t, \alpha, \beta, \gamma) + q. \underline{\bar{y}}(t, \alpha, \beta, \gamma)$$

$$\underline{\bar{y}}(t_0, \alpha, \beta, \gamma) = \bar{a} \quad \underline{\bar{y}}(T, \alpha, \beta, \gamma) = \bar{b}$$

$$\underline{y}''(t, \alpha, \beta, \gamma) = p. \underline{y}'(t, \alpha, \beta, \gamma) + q. \underline{y}(t, \alpha, \beta, \gamma)$$

$$\underline{y}(t_0, \alpha, \beta, \gamma) = \underline{a} \quad \underline{y}(T, \alpha, \beta, \gamma) = \underline{b}$$

Where, $\underline{\bar{y}}(t, \alpha) = v$ and $\underline{y}(t, \alpha) = u$

$$\underline{\bar{y}}''(t, \alpha, \beta, \gamma) = p. \underline{\bar{y}}'(t, \alpha, \beta, \gamma) + q. \underline{\bar{y}}(t, \alpha, \beta, \gamma) \tag{9}$$

$$\frac{u_{i+1}-2u_i+u_{i-1}}{h^2} = p \frac{v_{i+1}-v_{i-1}}{2h} + qv_i \tag{10}$$

$$u_{i+1} - 2u_i + u_{i-1} = \frac{ph}{2} v_{i+1} + qh^2 v_i - \frac{ph}{2} v_{i-1} \tag{11}$$

$$\begin{bmatrix} -2 & 1 & 0 \\ 1 & -2 & 1 \\ 0 & 1 & -2 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} u_1 \\ u_2 \\ u_3 \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} u_0 \\ 0 \\ u_4 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} qh^2 & \frac{ph}{2} & 0 \\ -\frac{ph}{2} & qh^2 & \frac{ph}{2} \\ 0 & -\frac{ph}{2} & qh^2 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} v_1 \\ v_2 \\ v_3 \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} -\frac{ph}{2} v_0 \\ 0 \\ \frac{ph}{2} v_4 \end{bmatrix} \tag{12}$$

$$\begin{bmatrix} -2 & 1 & 0 \\ 1 & -2 & 1 \\ 0 & 1 & -2 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} u_1 \\ u_2 \\ u_3 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} qh^2 & \frac{ph}{2} & 0 \\ -\frac{ph}{2} & qh^2 & \frac{ph}{2} \\ 0 & -\frac{ph}{2} & qh^2 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} v_1 \\ v_2 \\ v_3 \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} -\frac{ph}{2} v_0 - u_0 \\ 0 \\ \frac{ph}{2} v_4 - u_4 \end{bmatrix} \tag{13}$$

$$Au = Bv + C \tag{14}$$

$$A^{-1}Au = A^{-1}Bv + A^{-1}C \tag{15}$$

$$u = A^{-1}Bv + A^{-1}C \tag{16}$$

For the second equation

$$\underline{\bar{y}}''(t, \alpha, \beta, \gamma) = p. \underline{\bar{y}}'(t, \alpha, \beta, \gamma) + q. \underline{\bar{y}}(t, \alpha, \beta, \gamma) \tag{17}$$

$$\frac{v_{i+1}-2v_i+v_{i-1}}{h^2} = p \frac{u_{i+1}-u_{i-1}}{2h} + qu_i \tag{18}$$

$$v_{i+1} - 2v_i + v_{i-1} = \frac{ph}{2}u_{i+1} + qh^2u_i - \frac{ph}{2}u_{i-1} \tag{19}$$

$$\begin{bmatrix} -2 & 1 & 0 \\ 1 & -2 & 1 \\ 0 & 1 & -2 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} v_1 \\ v_2 \\ v_3 \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} v_0 \\ 0 \\ v_4 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} qh^2 & \frac{ph}{2} & 0 \\ -\frac{ph}{2} & qh^2 & \frac{ph}{2} \\ 0 & -\frac{ph}{2} & qh^2 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} u_1 \\ u_2 \\ u_3 \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} -\frac{ph}{2}u_0 \\ 0 \\ \frac{ph}{2}u_4 \end{bmatrix} \tag{20}$$

$$\begin{bmatrix} -2 & 1 & 0 \\ 1 & -2 & 1 \\ 0 & 1 & -2 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} v_1 \\ v_2 \\ v_3 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} qh^2 & \frac{ph}{2} & 0 \\ -\frac{ph}{2} & qh^2 & \frac{ph}{2} \\ 0 & -\frac{ph}{2} & qh^2 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} u_1 \\ u_2 \\ u_3 \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} -\frac{ph}{2}u_0 - v_0 \\ 0 \\ \frac{ph}{2}u_4 - v_4 \end{bmatrix} \tag{21}$$

$$Av = Bu + D \tag{22}$$

$$A^{-1}Av = A^{-1}Bu + A^{-1}D \tag{23}$$

$$v = A^{-1}Bu + A^{-1}D \tag{24}$$

By substituting the value of u

$$v = A^{-1}B(A^{-1}Bv + A^{-1}C) + A^{-1}D \tag{25}$$

$$(I - (A^{-1}B)^2)v = A^{-1}BA^{-1}C + A^{-1}D \tag{26}$$

$$v = [v_1 \quad v_2 \quad v_3]^T \tag{27}$$

$$u = [u_1 \quad u_2 \quad u_3]^T \tag{28}$$

C. Class (2,1)

$$\overline{y}''(t, \alpha, \beta, \gamma) = p. \overline{y}'(t, \alpha, \beta, \gamma) + q. \underline{y}(t, \alpha, \beta, \gamma),$$

$$\underline{y}(t_0, \alpha, \beta, \gamma) = \underline{a} \quad \underline{y}(T, \alpha, \beta, \gamma) = \underline{b},$$

$$\underline{y}''(t, \alpha, \beta, \gamma) = p. \underline{y}'(t, \alpha, \beta, \gamma) + q. \overline{y}(t, \alpha, \beta, \gamma),$$

$$\overline{y}(t_0, \alpha, \beta, \gamma) = \overline{a} \quad \overline{y}(T, \alpha, \beta, \gamma) = \overline{b}.$$

$$\overline{y}''(t, \alpha, \beta, \gamma) = p. \overline{y}'(t, \alpha, \beta, \gamma) + q. \underline{y}(t, \alpha, \beta, \gamma) \tag{29}$$

$$\frac{v_{i+1}-2v_i+v_{i-1}}{h^2} = p \frac{v_{i+1}-v_{i-1}}{2h} + qu_i \tag{30}$$

$$\left(1 - \frac{ph}{2}\right)v_{i+1} - 2v_i + \left(1 + \frac{ph}{2}\right)v_{i-1} = qh^2u_i \tag{31}$$

$$\begin{bmatrix} -2 & \left(1 - \frac{ph}{2}\right) & 0 \\ \left(1 + \frac{ph}{2}\right) & -2 & \left(1 - \frac{ph}{2}\right) \\ 0 & \left(1 + \frac{ph}{2}\right) & -2 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} v_1 \\ v_2 \\ v_3 \end{bmatrix} = qh^2 \begin{bmatrix} u_1 \\ u_2 \\ u_3 \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} -\left(1 + \frac{ph}{2}\right)v_0 \\ 0 \\ -\left(1 - \frac{ph}{2}\right)v_4 \end{bmatrix} \tag{32}$$

$$Av = qh^2u + B \tag{33}$$

$$v = A^{-1}qh^2u + A^{-1}B \tag{34}$$

For the second equation

$$\underline{y}''(t, \alpha, \beta, \gamma) = p. \underline{y}'(t, \alpha, \beta, \gamma) + q. \bar{y}(t, \alpha, \beta, \gamma) \tag{35}$$

$$\frac{u_{i+1} - 2u_i + u_{i-1}}{h^2} = p \frac{u_{i+1} - u_{i-1}}{2h} + qv_i \tag{36}$$

$$\left(1 - \frac{ph}{2}\right)u_{i+1} - 2u_i + \left(1 + \frac{ph}{2}\right)u_{i-1} = qh^2v_i \tag{37}$$

$$\begin{bmatrix} -2 & \left(1 - \frac{ph}{2}\right) & 0 \\ \left(1 + \frac{ph}{2}\right) & -2 & \left(1 - \frac{ph}{2}\right) \\ 0 & \left(1 + \frac{ph}{2}\right) & -2 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} v_1 \\ v_2 \\ v_3 \end{bmatrix} = qh^2 \begin{bmatrix} u_1 \\ u_2 \\ u_3 \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} -\left(1 + \frac{ph}{2}\right)u_0 \\ 0 \\ -\left(1 - \frac{ph}{2}\right)u_4 \end{bmatrix} \tag{38}$$

$$Au = qh^2v + C \tag{39}$$

$$u = A^{-1}qh^2v + A^{-1}C \tag{40}$$

By substitution the value of v

$$u = A^{-1}qh^2(A^{-1}qh^2u + A^{-1}B) + A^{-1}C \tag{41}$$

$$(1 - (qh^2)^2(A^{-1})^2)u = qh^2(A^{-1})^2B + A^{-1}C \tag{42}$$

Then,

$$v = [v_1 \quad v_2 \quad v_3]^T \tag{43}$$

$$u = [u_1 \quad u_2 \quad u_3]^T \tag{44}$$

D. Class (2,2)

$$\bar{y}''(t, \alpha, \beta, \gamma) = p. \underline{y}'(t, \alpha, \beta, \gamma) + q. \bar{y}(t, \alpha, \beta, \gamma)$$

$$\bar{y}(t_0, \alpha, \beta, \gamma) = \bar{a} \quad \bar{y}(T, \alpha, \beta, \gamma) = \bar{b}$$

$$\underline{y}''(t, \alpha, \beta, \gamma) = p. \bar{y}'(t, \alpha, \beta, \gamma) + q. \underline{y}(t, \alpha, \beta, \gamma)$$

$$\underline{y}(t_0, \alpha, \beta, \gamma) = \underline{a} \quad \underline{y}(T, \alpha, \beta, \gamma) = \underline{b}$$

$$\bar{y}''(t, \alpha, \beta, \gamma) = p. \underline{y}'(t, \alpha, \beta, \gamma) + q. \bar{y}(t, \alpha, \beta, \gamma) \tag{45}$$

$$\frac{v_{i+1} - 2v_i + v_{i-1}}{h^2} = p \frac{u_{i+1} - u_{i-1}}{2h} + qv_i \tag{46}$$

$$v_{i+1} - (2 + qh^2)v_i + v_{i-1} = \frac{ph}{2}u_{i+1} - \frac{ph}{2}u_{i-1} \tag{47}$$

$$\begin{bmatrix} -(2 + qh^2) & 1 & 0 \\ 1 & -(2 + qh^2) & 1 \\ 0 & 1 & -(2 + qh^2) \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} v_1 \\ v_2 \\ v_3 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & \frac{ph}{2} & 0 \\ -\frac{ph}{2} & 0 & \frac{ph}{2} \\ 0 & -\frac{ph}{2} & 0 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} u_1 \\ u_2 \\ u_3 \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} -\frac{ph}{2}u_0 - v_0 \\ 0 \\ \frac{ph}{2}u_4 - v_4 \end{bmatrix} \tag{48}$$

$$Av = Bu + C \tag{49}$$

$$A^{-1}Av = A^{-1}Bu + A^{-1}C \tag{50}$$

$$v = A^{-1}Bu + A^{-1}C \tag{51}$$

For the second equation,

$$\underline{y}''(t, \alpha, \beta, \gamma) = p \cdot \underline{y}'(t, \alpha, \beta, \gamma) + q \cdot \underline{y}(t, \alpha, \beta, \gamma) \tag{52}$$

$$\frac{u_{i+1} - 2u_i + u_{i-1}}{h^2} = p \frac{v_{i+1} - v_{i-1}}{2h} + qu_i \tag{53}$$

$$u_{i+1} - (2 + qh^2)u_i + u_{i-1} = \frac{ph}{2}v_{i+1} - \frac{ph}{2}v_{i-1} \tag{54}$$

$$\begin{bmatrix} -(2 + qh^2) & 1 & 0 \\ 1 & -(2 + qh^2) & 1 \\ 0 & 1 & -(2 + qh^2) \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} u_1 \\ u_2 \\ u_3 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & \frac{ph}{2} & 0 \\ -\frac{ph}{2} & 0 & \frac{ph}{2} \\ 0 & -\frac{ph}{2} & 0 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} v_1 \\ v_2 \\ v_3 \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} -\frac{ph}{2}v_0 - u_0 \\ 0 \\ \frac{ph}{2}v_4 - u_4 \end{bmatrix} \tag{55}$$

$$Au = Bv + C \tag{56}$$

$$A^{-1}Au = A^{-1}Bv + A^{-1}C \tag{57}$$

$$u = A^{-1}Bv + A^{-1}C \tag{58}$$

4. Numerical Simulation

In this section, the utility of the proposed method is examined by presenting an example, whose analytical solutions are provided in the previous work [19]. To validate the efficiency of the proposed technique, the numerical results are compared with the exact solution [19]. The absolute error can be formulated as:

- The absolute error E_N of the solution is defined by:

$$|e_N| = |\mathbf{Exact} - \mathbf{Approximation}|.$$

4.1 Example 1

$$\widetilde{y}''(t) = 4\widetilde{y}'(t) + 5\widetilde{y}(t)$$

$$\widetilde{y}(t_0) = \widetilde{a} = (0.8, 1, 1.4; 0.8, 0.2, 0.3)$$

$$\tilde{y}(T) = \tilde{b} = (2.6, 3, 3.1, ; 0.8, 0.2, 0.3)$$

p = 4 & q = 5

- **Case (1, 1)**

Analytical Solution

Table (1): *The Analytical Results of Upper and Lower for (α, β, γ) at $t = 0.7$*

α	$\underline{y}(0.7, \alpha)$	$\bar{y}(0.7, \alpha)$	β	$\underline{y}(0.7, \beta)$	$\bar{y}(0.7, \beta)$	γ	$\underline{y}(0.7, \gamma)$	$\bar{y}(0.7, \gamma)$
0.0	0.884039	1.287469	0.2	1.060290	1.060290	0.3	1.060290	1.060290
0.2	0.928101	1.230675	0.4	1.016227	1.117085	0.5	1.009932	1.125198
0.4	0.972164	1.173880	0.6	0.972164	1.173880	0.7	0.959575	1.190107
0.6	1.016227	1.117085	0.8	0.928101	1.230675	0.9	0.934396	1.255015
0.8	1.060290	1.060290	1.0	0.884039	1.287469	1.0	0.884039	1.287469

Approximation Solution and the Related Errors

Table (2): *The Approximation Results of Upper and Lower for (α, β, γ) at $t = 0.7$ at $N = 50$.*

α	$\underline{y}(0.7, \alpha)$	$\bar{y}(0.7, \alpha)$	β	$\underline{y}(0.7, \beta)$	$\bar{y}(0.7, \beta)$	γ	$\underline{y}(0.7, \gamma)$	$\bar{y}(0.7, \gamma)$
0.0	0.883563	1.286953	0.2	1.059750	1.059750	0.3	1.060290	1.060290
0.2	0.927609	1.230153	0.4	1.015703	1.116551	0.5	1.009411	1.124665
0.4	0.971656	1.173352	0.6	0.971656	1.173352	0.7	0.959072	1.189581
0.6	1.015703	1.116551	0.8	0.927609	1.230153	0.9	0.908732	1.254496
0.8	1.059750	1.059750	1.0	0.883563	1.286953	1.0	0.884039	1.287469

Table (3): *The Errors Results of Upper and Lower for (α, β, γ) at $t = 0.7$ at $N = 50$.*

α	$\underline{e}(0.7, \alpha)$	$\bar{e}(0.7, \alpha)$	β	$\underline{e}(0.7, \beta)$	$\bar{e}(0.7, \beta)$	γ	$\underline{e}(0.7, \gamma)$	$\bar{e}(0.7, \gamma)$
0.0	4.76 E-04	5.16 E-04	0.2	5.40 E-04	5.40 E-04	0.3	5.40 E-04	5.40 E-04
0.2	4.92 E-04	5.22 E-04	0.4	5.24 E-04	5.34 E-04	0.5	5.22 E-04	5.33 E-04
0.4	5.08 E-04	5.28 E-04	0.6	5.08 E-04	5.28 E-04	0.7	5.03 E-04	5.26 E-04
0.6	5.24 E-04	5.34 E-04	0.8	4.92 E-04	5.22 E-04	0.9	4.85 E-04	5.19 E-04
0.8	5.40 E-04	5.40 E-04	1.0	4.76 E-04	5.16 E-04	1.0	4.76 E-04	5.16 E-04

The analytical results for t=0.7 are shown in Table 1, followed by the approximation results for various values of N in Tables 2, 4, and 6, and finally the error between analytical and numerical results in Tables 3, 5, and 7.

Table (4): The Approximation Results of Upper and Lower for (α, β, γ) at $t = 0.7$ at $N = 100$.

α	$\underline{y}(0.7, \alpha)$	$\bar{y}(0.7, \alpha)$	β	$\underline{y}(0.7, \beta)$	$\bar{y}(0.7, \beta)$	γ	$\underline{y}(0.7, \gamma)$	$\bar{y}(0.7, \gamma)$
0.0	0.883920	1.287341	0.2	1.060155	1.060155	0.3	1.060155	1.060155
0.2	0.927979	1.230544	0.4	1.016096	1.116951	0.5	1.009802	1.125065
0.4	0.972037	1.173748	0.6	0.972037	1.173748	0.7	0.959449	1.189975
0.6	1.016096	1.116951	0.8	0.927979	1.230544	0.9	0.909096	1.254885
0.8	1.060155	1.060155	1.0	0.883920	1.287341	1.0	0.883920	1.287341

Table (5): The Errors Results of Upper and Lower for (α, β, γ) at $t = 0.7$ at $N = 100$.

α	$\underline{e}(0.7, \alpha)$	$\bar{e}(0.7, \alpha)$	β	$\underline{e}(0.7, \beta)$	$\bar{e}(0.7, \beta)$	γ	$\underline{e}(0.7, \gamma)$	$\bar{e}(0.7, \gamma)$
0.0	1.19 E-04	1.29 E-04	0.2	1.35 E-04	1.35 E-04	0.3	1.35 E-04	1.35 E-04
0.2	1.23 E-04	1.30 E-04	0.4	1.31 E-04	1.33 E-04	0.5	1.30 E-04	1.33 E-04
0.4	1.27 E-04	1.32 E-04	0.6	1.27 E-04	1.32 E-04	0.7	1.26 E-04	1.31 E-04
0.6	1.31 E-04	1.33 E-04	0.8	1.23 E-04	1.31 E-04	0.9	1.21 E-04	1.30 E-04
0.8	1.35 E-04	1.35 E-04	1.0	1.19 E-04	1.29 E-04	1.0	1.19 E-04	1.29 E-04

$N = 200$ & $h = 0.005$

Table (6): The Approximation Results of Upper and Lower for (α, β, γ) at $t = 0.7$ at $N = 200$.

α	$\underline{y}(0.7, \alpha)$	$\bar{y}(0.7, \alpha)$	β	$\underline{y}(0.7, \beta)$	$\bar{y}(0.7, \beta)$	γ	$\underline{y}(0.7, \gamma)$	$\bar{y}(0.7, \gamma)$
0.0	0.884009	1.287437	0.2	1.060256	1.060256	0.3	1.060256	1.060256
0.2	0.928071	1.230642	0.4	1.016194	1.117052	0.5	1.009900	1.125165
0.4	0.972133	1.173847	0.6	0.972133	1.173847	0.7	0.959544	1.190074
0.6	1.016194	1.117052	0.8	0.928071	1.230642	0.9	0.909187	1.254983
0.8	1.060256	1.060256	1.0	0.884009	1.287437	1.0	0.884009	1.287437

Table (7): The Errors Results of Upper and Lower for (α, β, γ) at $t = 0.7$ at $N = 200$.

α	$\underline{e}(0.7, \alpha)$	$\bar{e}(0.7, \alpha)$	β	$\underline{e}(0.7, \beta)$	$\bar{e}(0.7, \beta)$	γ	$\underline{e}(0.7, \gamma)$	$\bar{e}(0.7, \gamma)$
0.0	2.97 E-05	3.22 E-05	0.2	3.37 E-05	3.37 E-05	0.3	3.37 E-05	3.37 E-05

0.2	3.07 E-05	3.26 E-05	0.4	3.27E-05	3.33 E-05	0.5	3.26 E-05	3.33 E-05
0.4	3.17 E-05	3.30 E-05	0.6	3.17 E-05	3.30 E-05	0.7	3.14 E-05	3.29 E-05
0.6	3.27E-05	3.33 E-05	0.8	3.07 E-05	3.26 E-05	0.9	3.03 E-05	3.24 E-05
0.8	3.37 E-05	3.37 E-05	1.0	2.97 E-05	3.22 E-05	1.0	2.97 E-05	3.22 E-05

Figure 1: Surface of Absolute Error for Lower Case (1,1) Alpha

Figure 2: Surface of Absolute Error for Upper Case (1,1) Alpha

Figure 3: Surface of Absolute Error for Lower Case (1,1) Beta

Figure 4: Surface of Absolute error for Upper Case (1,1) Beta

Figure 5: Surface of Absolute Error for Lower Case (1,1) Gamma

Figure 6: Surface of Absolute Error for Upper Case (1,1) Gamma

Figures 1 to 6 show the surface of errors at $N=200$, $t \in [0.1: 0.9]$, with values of (α, β, γ) .

Case (1, 2)

Analytical Solution

Table (8): The Analytical Results of Upper and Lower for (α, β, γ) at $t = 0.7$

α	$\underline{y}(0.7, \alpha)$	$\bar{y}(0.7, \alpha)$	β	$\underline{y}(0.7, \beta)$	$\bar{y}(0.7, \beta)$	γ	$\underline{y}(0.7, \gamma)$	$\bar{y}(0.7, \gamma)$
0.0	0.762704	1.408804	0.2	1.060290	1.060290	0.3	1.060290	1.060290
0.2	0.837101	1.321675	0.4	0.985893	1.147418	0.5	0.975265	1.159865
0.4	0.911497	1.234547	0.6	0.911497	1.234547	0.7	0.890241	1.259441
0.6	0.985893	1.147418	0.8	0.837101	1.321675	0.9	0.805217	1.359016
0.8	1.060290	1.060290	1.0	0.762704	1.408804	1.0	0.762704	1.408804

Approximation Solution at $N = 200$ & $h = 0.005$

Table (9): The Approximation Results of Upper and Lower for (α, β, γ) at $t = 0.7$ for $N = 200$

α	$\underline{y}(0.7, \alpha)$	$\bar{y}(0.7, \alpha)$	β	$\underline{y}(0.7, \beta)$	$\bar{y}(0.7, \beta)$	γ	$\underline{y}(0.7, \gamma)$	$\bar{y}(0.7, \gamma)$
0.0	0.762672	1.408774	0.2	1.060256	1.060256	0.3	1.060256	1.060256
0.2	0.837068	1.321645	0.4	0.985860	1.147386	0.5	0.975232	1.159833
0.4	0.911464	1.234515	0.6	0.911464	1.234515	0.7	0.890208	1.259409
0.6	0.985860	1.147386	0.8	0.837068	1.321645	0.9	0.805184	1.358986
0.8	1.060256	1.060256	1.0	0.762672	1.408774	1.0	0.762672	1.408774

Error at N = 200

Table (10): The Error Results of Upper and Lower for (α, β, γ) at $t = 0.7$ at $N = 200$.

α	$\underline{e}(0.7, \alpha)$	$\bar{e}(0.7, \alpha)$	β	$\underline{e}(0.7, \beta)$	$\bar{e}(0.7, \beta)$	γ	$\underline{e}(0.7, \gamma)$	$\bar{e}(0.7, \gamma)$
0.0	3.258E-05	2.935E-05	0.2	3.372E-05	3.372E-05	0.3	3.372E-05	3.372E-05
0.2	3.285E-05	3.044E-05	0.4	3.344E-05	3.263E-05	0.5	3.340E-05	3.247E-05
0.4	3.315E-05	3.153E-05	0.6	3.315E-05	3.153E-05	0.7	3.307E-05	3.122E-05
0.6	3.344E-05	3.263E-05	0.8	3.285E-05	3.044E-05	0.9	3.274E-05	2.997E-05
0.8	3.372E-05	3.372E-05	1.0	3.258E-05	2.935E-05	1.0	3.258E-05	2.935E-05

- Case (2, 1)

Analytical Solution

Table (11): The Analytical Results of Upper and Lower for (α, β, γ) at $t = 0.7$

α	$\underline{y}(0.7, \alpha)$	$\bar{y}(0.7, \alpha)$	β	$\underline{y}(0.7, \beta)$	$\bar{y}(0.7, \beta)$	γ	$\underline{y}(0.7, \gamma)$	$\bar{y}(0.7, \gamma)$
0.0	0.638923	1.532585	0.2	1.060290	1.060290	0.3	1.060290	1.060290
0.2	0.744265	1.414511	0.4	0.954948	1.178364	0.5	0.939899	1.195231
0.4	0.849607	1.296438	0.6	0.849607	1.296438	0.7	0.819509	1.330173
0.6	0.954948	1.178364	0.8	0.744265	1.414511	0.9	0.699119	1.465114
0.8	1.060290	1.060290	1.0	0.638923	1.532585	1.0	0.638923	1.532585

Approximation Solution

Table (12): The Approximation Results of Upper and Lower for (α, β, γ) at $t = 0.7$ at $N = 150$.

α	$\underline{y}(0.7, \alpha)$	$\bar{y}(0.7, \alpha)$	β	$\underline{y}(0.7, \beta)$	$\bar{y}(0.7, \beta)$	γ	$\underline{y}(0.7, \gamma)$	$\bar{y}(0.7, \gamma)$
0.0	0.638851	1.532546	0.2	1.060230	1.060230	0.3	1.060230	1.060230
0.2	0.744196	1.414467	0.4	0.954885	1.178309	0.5	0.939836	1.195178
0.4	0.849541	1.296388	0.6	0.849541	1.296388	0.7	0.819442	1.330125
0.6	0.954885	1.178309	0.8	0.744196	1.414467	0.9	0.699048	1.465073
0.8	1.060230	1.060230	1.0	0.638851	1.532546	1.0	0.638851	1.532546

Error at N = 150

Table (13): The Error Results of Upper and Lower for (α, β, γ) at $t = 0.7$ at $N = 150$.

α	$\underline{e}(0.7, \alpha)$	$\bar{e}(0.7, \alpha)$	β	$\underline{e}(0.7, \beta)$	$\bar{e}(0.7, \beta)$	γ	$\underline{e}(0.7, \gamma)$	$\bar{e}(0.7, \gamma)$
0.0	7.18 E-05	3.83 E-05	0.2	6.00 E-05	5.60 E-05	0.3	6.00 E-05	5.60 E-05
0.2	6.88 E-05	4.37 E-05	0.4	6.29 E-05	5.45 E-05	0.5	6.33 E-05	5.37 E-05
0.4	6.58 E-05	4.91 E-05	0.6	6.58 E-05	4.91 E-05	0.7	6.67 E-05	4.76 E-05
0.6	6.29 E-05	5.45 E-05	0.8	6.88 E-05	4.37 E-05	0.9	7.00 E-05	4.14 E-05
0.8	6.00 E-05	5.60 E-05	1.0	7.18 E-05	3.83 E-05	1.0	7.18 E-05	3.83 E-05

• Case (2, 2)

Analytical Solution

Table (14): The Analytical Results of Upper and Lower for (α, β, γ) at $t = 0.7$

α	$\underline{y}(0.7, \alpha)$	$\bar{y}(0.7, \alpha)$	β	$\underline{y}(0.7, \beta)$	$\bar{y}(0.7, \beta)$	γ	$\underline{y}(0.7, \gamma)$	$\bar{y}(0.7, \gamma)$
0.0	0.880422	1.291087	0.2	1.060290	1.060290	0.3	1.060290	1.060290
0.2	0.925389	1.233387	0.4	1.015323	1.117989	0.5	1.008899	1.126231
0.4	0.970356	1.175688	0.6	0.970356	1.175688	0.7	0.957508	1.192174
0.6	1.015323	1.117989	0.8	0.925389	1.233387	0.9	0.906117	1.258116
0.8	1.060290	1.060290	1.0	0.880422	1.291087	1.0	0.880422	1.291087

Approximation Solution at $N = 200$ & $h = 0.005$

Table (15): The Approximation Results of Upper and Lower for (α, β, γ) at $t = 0.7$ at $N = 200$.

α	$\underline{y}(0.7, \alpha)$	$\bar{y}(0.7, \alpha)$	β	$\underline{y}(0.7, \beta)$	$\bar{y}(0.7, \beta)$	γ	$\underline{y}(0.7, \gamma)$	$\bar{y}(0.7, \gamma)$
0.0	0.880391	1.291055	0.2	1.060256	1.060256	0.3	1.060256	1.060256
0.2	0.925357	1.233355	0.4	1.015290	1.117956	0.5	1.008866	1.126198
0.4	0.970324	1.175656	0.6	0.970324	1.175656	0.7	0.957476	1.192141
0.6	1.015290	1.117956	0.8	0.925357	1.233355	0.9	0.906086	1.258084
0.8	1.060256	1.060256	1.0	0.880391	1.291055	1.0	0.880391	1.291055

Error at N = 200

Table (16): *The Error Results of Upper and Lower for (α, β, γ) at $t = 0.7$ at $N = 200$.*

α	$\underline{e}(0.7, \alpha)$	$\bar{e}(0.7, \alpha)$	β	$\underline{e}(0.7, \beta)$	$\bar{e}(0.7, \beta)$	γ	$\underline{e}(0.7, \gamma)$	$\bar{e}(0.7, \gamma)$
0.0	3.06 E-05	3.14 E-05	0.2	3.37 E-05	3.37 E-05	0.3	3.37 E-05	3.37 E-05
0.2	3.14 E-05	3.20 E-05	0.4	3.29 E-05	3.31 E-05	0.5	3.28 E-05	3.30 E-05
0.4	3.21 E-05	3.25 E-05	0.6	3.21 E-05	3.25 E-05	0.7	3.19 E-05	3.23 E-05
0.6	3.29 E-05	3.31 E-05	0.8	3.14 E-05	3.20 E-05	0.9	3.10 E-05	3.17 E-05
0.8	3.37 E-05	3.37 E-05	1.0	3.06 E-05	3.14 E-05	1.0	3.06 E-05	3.14 E-05

Conclusion:

In this paper, the numerical solution of the second-order differential equation under the effect of a neutrosophic environment in the boundary condition has been developed. The finite difference method and the generalized Hukuhara differentiability are applied to present the approximate solution of each one of the four classes of the solution. The results of the proposed solution are compared with the analytical solution of the same problem even after applying generalized Hukuhara differentiability. It is found that by decreasing the step size, the error is decreased, and it can be classified as an acceptable error when it reaches 10^{-6} at $h = 0.005$. In future work, new numerical progressed methods will be presented and applied for numerical application to investigate if it will enhance the error in such an uncertain environment.

Acknowledgment

The authors would like to express their gratitude to Prof. Dr. Florentine Smarandache [The father of Neutrosophic Logic], and his support in publishing this article.

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Received: June 3, 2023. Accepted: Oct 1, 2023